

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KORLISON****FIRST NAME: ROCHEFORTE****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

THE FOUNDATION FOR ARCHIEVING SUCCESS IS THROUGH WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The decision to seek admission in the postgraduate program of Doctorate in Sustainability Development and Diplomacy (DSDD) with Euclid University came with lots of trepidations. It was never a thought process that it is going to be easy; out of the abundance of materials, reading from the course syllabus and getting accustomed to the Learning Management System (LMS) shows that the path towards building this portfolio remains a challenge. It became clear that the territory I intended to venture on was filled with tedious exercises of different writing styles, continuous improvements, and critical analysis. Knowing that an opportunity to enter a doctoral program at any university, will be bearing testimony to the words of Francis Bacon “reading maketh a full man; writing maketh an exact man.” Being an “exact man” requires a lot of writing in this sphere. In this case, I found out that Euclid University offers the perfect backdrop from whence, I can feel uniquely fitted unto a pathway that will not only introduced me to the concept of the course work as presented in *Euclid University ACA-401D Coursepack* but also strengthen my ability to build perfect writing skills set that will be useful throughout this study and even beyond.

Over the years of my professional sojourn, I have been tested by writing few articles, and journals. But nothing seems to be perfect; giving the fact that many of those writings lacks, the sufficiency of the material in the clear sense of what a successful writing should be; in terms of style as specified in the many ongoing researches in sustainable development and with climate change being at the heist of this study, it is a known fact that

many contributions will be introduced or made from many sources. It is fair and honest that we build upon the works of others in this field at the same time we recognized their contributions by reinforcing the academic policy on plagiarism. It is noteworthy that we followed through this exercise always with sound judgment, professional clarity and reliability. Being true in mind that any piece of writing should fundamentally address the substantive concepts which maximized the elements of a good writing: free from plagiarism, good grammar, and accurate citations. Remember, plagiarism can take one or two forms: intentional or unintentional (Turabian 2009, 10)

2) THE MECHANICS OF WRITING

A great writer is not recognized simply by the captivating title of his or her work. Rather, the embodiment of what is told, how it is told makes a whole lot difference in who this known author is or stand to become. How credible you become when your piece is read says a lot about who you are. Therefore, mastering the mechanics of writing is a unique approach to ensuing what a writer wants his or her audience to understand or know of the author. The mechanics include from formatting the right style, avoiding plagiarism, using the right citations, and recognizing and the usage of appropriate grammar. Continue with reviewing the various paragraphs, sentences, individual wording, spelling, punctuation, and grammar (Houghton 2009, 11).

Once a writer appreciates and understands these constructive clues and judgment in writing the more palatable and digestive his writing will be and free of unilateral opinion. To shape the paradigm of thoughts, a writing must demonstrate a thorough scope of research; aim with the purpose of advancing new knowledge or expanding on already existing ones (Turabian 2007, 5-11). How well we make of this interpretation of our ideas stands out, the less criticism and more credible our writing.

3) COPYRIGHT OR COPY-HEAD

No matter how long or aged the source of an information is, it must be known that there was once an author of the idea or there is an author. This source might be in speech or in essays. It is meant in academia to give credit to whom credit is due. As often said in biblical chapters “give to Caesar what is Caesar; and to God what belongs to God” and “there is nothing new under the heavens”. So, to assume that an idea has no source, it is only an attempt to be fool-headed and a display of total disregard for authorship. Whenever, this occurs, professionals see it as plagiarism. It is very well mentioned that it is a serious academic offence that can have serious consequences if anyone list or cite an idea without the source as described in *Euclid University ACA-401D Coursepack*. It is not only unethical but deprived the source of the credibility and the attention they deserve. Hence, if one of the oldest and more public and readable text – the “Bible” has commanded that we duly recognized the recognizable. Therefore, it is prudent that we guard against inadvertent plagiarism (Turabian 2007, 77).

4) BRINGING IT TOGETHER

It was a yearlong of reflection before I finally came to agree with the realization that I wanted to pursue the post-graduate program with a doctorate in sustainable development and diplomacy. Being an ardent participant and activist for sustainable practices, I researched many programs and universities globally to find an institution that was offering a study on the environment 100% online at the same time taking care of my domestics as a parent. Euclid University stood as the door for such opened challenge. I reviewed the program of study overtimes and all the core works, templates and learning tools: LMS and Course Management System (CMS) before I finally made the decision (EUCLID 2015).

Though I am still working on mastering the content of the learning tool and studying academic requirement including assignment, I continue to hope that in coming weeks and months leading to thesis writing, I will attain more confidence of the materials and become less perturb by bringing it all together. The entire process involved the comprehensive ability to properly cite the ideas, word, or findings of others in their work. This is done to give proper credit to those deserving it, assure readers of information accuracy, and aid readers in following and expanding upon the research (Turabian 2009, 41).

The focus of what will become of a great research is fundamentally linked to the evasive concept of what an author or researcher seeks to put out. I am in no way indifferent to the goal of expanding new frontiers of ideas. Rather, I am deeply troubled if basic systems such as notes and bibliography for citing sources are ignored. The paramount goal of either system is to give credit to deserving authors and allow readers to locate published or unpublished material utilized within the writing (Turabian 2009, 41).

5) CONCLUSION

The foundation for achieving success through writing comes with painstaking exercises of thoroughness. I referred to it as borderless exercise because knowledge and time keep on evolving with research, and new challenges. As the result, individuals striving of excellence in academia must be prepared to bear a significant burden of the exercise. I continue to champion and seek the prospects that put me in the state of continuous relevance thereby appreciating and utilizing any opportunity that enhances my achievement in becoming a professional with focus on a discipline. Despite many professional schools of thoughts that have advance different formats: MLA, APA, Rubic etcetera, what matters most is one's ability to stick to the very specific format and style of writing that your discipline will demand during your course of study. Again, regardless of whatever format and style, one general caveat that is intellectually unacceptable is Plagiarism and what is intellectually appropriate is good grammar. Therefore, I recommend further that consistency is key to the end of the program.

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